

Supplementary Material

UAV Delivery Business Models within U-Space: Empirical Evidence from Institutional Adoption Readiness in a Medium-Sized Polish City

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S1. SESAR U-Space Demonstration Projects Validating Healthcare UAV Delivery

Healthcare's leading adoption interest (36.36%) receives operational validation from SESAR-funded demonstration projects within U-Space.

Table S1. SESAR U-Space Demonstration Projects

Project	Location	Period	Route Type	Key Result
BURDI	Kempen region, Belgium	2022–2025	Hospital-to-hospital BVLOS	Ground transport time reduced from ~30 min to <13 min
SAFIR-Med	Antwerp, Belgium	2021–2023	Urban hospital-to-hospital BVLOS	First SORA-compliant BVLOS delivery between urban hospitals

S2. Cross-European Corroboration of Safety as Primary Adoption Driver

The central role of perceived safety ($U=933.50$, $r=-0.42$) receives corroboration from multiple European studies. Kellermann et al. [4] conducted a population-representative telephone survey in Germany ($n=819$) and found perceived safety risk as a significant negative predictor, with only 25% of Germans supporting drone delivery. Wang et al. [10], surveying Swiss drone professionals, found safety received the highest average ranking score (2.59) among all acceptance factors. The cross-European survey by Stolz et al. [9] ($n=2,998$ across six countries) demonstrated that acceptance strongly depends on use case, with knowledge about drones proving an essential predictor. The MUSE/SESAR study (Krstić Simić et al. [5]) reinforced this, finding stakeholder consensus that the extent to which citizens are informed about UAM operations is pivotal for acceptance.

S3. Comparative Synthesis of UAV Adoption Factor Frameworks

Table S2. Comparative Synthesis of Adoption Factors

Study	Framework	Top Factors	Convergence
This study	Mann-Whitney U	Expected benefits ($r=-0.51$), safety ($r=-0.42$), trust ($r=-0.36$)	—
Ali et al. [1]	Integrated TOE+DOI	Cost parameters (0.217), strategic alliances (0.166), competitive pressures (0.123)	Benefits \approx cost-benefit assessment at organizational level

Maghazei et al. [6]	Longitudinal multi-case	Use-case identification, technology-organization fit	Sectoral variation reflects differential use-case clarity
Marfo et al. [7]	TAM-based survey (n=330)	Technology adoption, user satisfaction, environmental factors	Institutional satisfaction aligns with expected benefits driver

S4. U-Space Implementation Gap and Polish Market Context

As of early 2024, no U-Space areas had been designated in any EU member state despite Regulation 2021/664 entering into force in January 2023 [8]. The first EASA-certified U-Space Service Provider (ANRA Technologies) received certification only in May 2025. Poland recorded 668,786 drone operations with 222,086 registered operators in 2023 (Gugała-Szczerbicka and Fortońska [2]), demonstrating a rapidly maturing market ecosystem. The Polish White Paper's emphasis on medium-sized cities as testbeds reflects a deliberate strategy where lower airspace congestion and more manageable regulatory coordination create conditions for early business model deployment.

S5. Small-Sample Sectoral Data (n<10, excluded from main paper)

Three NACE sections had samples below n=10 and were excluded from the poster's percentage-based analysis: Section D (Energy supply, n=1, 1 interested, 100%), Section L (Real estate, n=3, 1 interested, 33.33%), and Section N (Administrative services, n=8, 2 interested, 25.00%). These are reported here for completeness; percentage-based interpretation is not warranted given the sample sizes.

S6. Demographic Dimensions

A gender dimension was observed: 75% of interested decision-makers were male ($\chi^2(4, N=181)=13.198, p<0.05, V_c=0.270$). This suggests that business model communication strategies should account for demographic variation in technology receptiveness. Stolz et al. [9] found age and knowledge about drones as significant predictors, while Henderson [3] found that unmanned aircraft users (n=767, New Zealand) generally considered regulatory information accessible. These findings suggest service providers should invest in targeted awareness programs for underrepresented demographic groups among institutional decision-makers.

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